

Correlation of Selected Psychological Skills and Sports Performance Enhancement among Government Secondary School Students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Lga of Rivers State

Ochor Daniel Chinonso & Udemé Bassey-John

Department of Sport and Exercise Science
Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt
Choba, Port Harcourt Rivers State.
ochordaniel@gmail.com, 08161678408

ABSTRACT

This research investigated the correlation of selected psychological skills and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State. The study was guided by five (5) objectives while five (5) research questions were answered. The correlational research design was used for the study. The population of the study consisted all public secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni local government area of Rivers State. A sample size of 450 secondary school students was used for the study. The proportionate stratified random sampling technique was used with 30% of the population of each of the selected school to draw the sample. The instrument for data collection was a 30-item self-structured questionnaire with reliability coefficient of 0.72. Mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment correlation were used for data analysis. The study revealed that motivation self-confidence, concentration, goal setting, and stress management had positive and significant relationship with sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni local government area of Rivers State. The researcher recommended among others that sports administrators and coaches should integrate training modules on motivation, self-confidence, concentration, goal-setting, and stress management into their regular training programs as these skills will aid athlete development. Sports masters and coaches should also implement a system for regularly monitoring and evaluating the psychological skill development of student-athletes. This can help in identifying areas that need further improvement and in tailoring training programs to meet the specific needs of the athletes

Keywords: Psychological Skills, Sports Performance, Secondary School Students, Competitive Sports, Athletic Success and Mental Training.

Introduction

The promotion of sports among secondary school students is essential for their comprehensive development, which includes physical, mental, and social aspects. The focus on psychological abilities in improving sports performance has grown, due to their substantial influence on players' achievements in competitive settings. Psychological factors such as drive, self-assurance, concentration, and stress control play a crucial role in determining athletic success. These skills not only enhance performance but also contribute to the holistic personal growth of the students (Weinberg & Gould, 2019). Secondary school pupils in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (LGA) in Rivers State, Nigeria, have shown an increasing enthusiasm for sports. Nevertheless, the precise correlation between psychological abilities and athletic achievement in this particular scenario has not been thoroughly investigated.

Psychological abilities play a crucial role for athletes as they manage the demands and difficulties of competitive sports. These skills have the potential to greatly impact multiple facets of sports performance, encompassing: (1) Motivation, defined as the internal force that propels individuals to engage in training, enhance their skills, and participate in competitions, is essential for achieving athletic success. Motivation can be categorized as either intrinsic, which is motivated by internal factors, or extrinsic, which is impacted by external rewards (Ryan & Deci, 2020). (2) Self-Confidence, as defined by Vealey and Chase (2016), refers to the belief in one's own talents, which can improve performance and help athletes face challenges and bounce back from disappointments. (3) Focus and Concentration: This refers to the capacity to sustain attention and mental focus when engaging in training and competition. It is crucial for performing tasks with precision and making well-thought-out strategic choices (Weinberg & Gould, 2019). (4) Stress Management: Research indicates that effectively managing anxiety and stress is a crucial psychological ability for sustaining peak performance, particularly in high-pressure situations (Hanton et al., 2015). (5) Goal Setting: Establishing attainable and realistic objectives aids athletes in maintaining concentration and drive, while also creating a distinct trajectory for growth and triumph (Locke & Latham, 2019).

Psychological skills play a pivotal role in sports performance by enhancing athletes' ability to cope with the demands of training and competition. These skills include motivation, self-

confidence, focus, concentration, stress management, and goal setting. Athletes who develop strong psychological skills are better equipped to handle the pressure of competition, maintain focus during critical moments, and recover from setbacks more effectively. For instance, motivation drives athletes to persist through rigorous training and strive for continuous improvement. Self-confidence enables them to believe in their abilities and take on challenges with a positive mindset (Vealey & Chase, 2016).

Furthermore, psychological skills contribute to an athlete's mental toughness, which is essential for peak performance in high-pressure situations. Mental toughness involves resilience, determination, and the ability to stay composed under stress. Athletes who possess these qualities are more likely to perform consistently and achieve their goals. Coaches and sports psychologists emphasize the development of psychological skills through various training programs, as these skills not only enhance performance but also contribute to the overall well-being and longevity of an athlete's career (Gucciardi et al., 2009).

Studies have demonstrated that athletes who cultivate robust psychological abilities generally achieve superior performance, experience expedited recovery from injuries, and enjoy lengthier and more prosperous careers (Gucciardi et al., 2009). Hence, comprehending and improving these abilities can significantly influence the athletic performance of high school kids. Sports are integral to the extracurricular programs of many institutions, with football, athletics, basketball, and volleyball being especially favored. Inter-school sports tournaments are frequently held in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA schools, promoting a sense of competitiveness and camaraderie among pupils (Amaele & Enunwaonye, 2020). Nevertheless, even with active engagement in sports, there is a requirement for organized programs to build psychological abilities in order to further enhance sports performance.

Evaluating psychological abilities in athletes encompasses a blend of self-report surveys, behavioral monitoring, and performance evaluations. The Sports Mental Toughness Questionnaire (SMTQ) is a commonly employed test that assesses an athlete's mental toughness in different aspects, including confidence, constancy, and control (Sheard et al., 2009). The SMTQ assists coaches and psychologists in identifying specific areas in which athletes may require additional growth and customizing interventions accordingly.

Another prevalent approach involves performance profiling, in which athletes evaluate their proficiency in specific psychological skills and compare their self-assessments with those made by their coaches or peers. This methodology offers a holistic assessment of an athlete's capabilities and limitations, aiding in the establishment of specific objectives for enhancement. Behavioral observations during training and competition offer vital insights into an athlete's psychological condition. Coaches can assess athletes' reactions to pressure, their ability to handle stress, and their capacity to keep concentration. This valuable information can then be utilized by coaches to offer constructive criticism and create customized training programs (Weinberg & Gould, 2019).

The sports performance of secondary school children is impacted by a range of factors that can be broadly classified into the areas of physical, psychological, social, and environmental influences. From a physical standpoint, performance is greatly influenced by aspects such as fitness level, skill mastery, nutrition, and overall health. Thorough training and appropriate conditioning are essential for cultivating the physical attributes necessary for sports. Nutrition is crucial in providing athletes with the essential energy and nutrients needed for optimal performance (McArdle et al., 2015).

Mentally, motivation, self-assurance, concentration, and stress control are crucial factors that influence performance. Various social elements, such as familial, peer, and coaching support, have the potential to impact an athlete's performance in either a beneficial or detrimental manner. Receiving support and helpful criticism from these sources can enhance morale and motivation. Environmental factors, including the presence of facilities, the caliber of coaching, and the availability of equipment, also exert a substantial influence. The scholastic milieu, encompassing both scholastic obligations and temporal organization, can impact an athlete's capacity to prepare and perform optimally (Weinberg & Gould, 2019).

The correlation between psychological skills and sports performance is extensively documented, with multiple research emphasizing the beneficial influence of mental talents on athletic results. Psychological abilities such as drive, self-assurance, concentration, and stress control are crucial for an athlete's capacity to excel under stress and sustain regularity. Athletes that possess elevated degrees of self-assurance are more inclined to approach tournaments with a favorable

mental attitude, hence augmenting their performance (Vealey & Chase, 2016). Athletes are driven to train harder and remain committed to their sport by both intrinsic and external motivation. Research has demonstrated that those who are motivated intrinsically, meaning they are driven by internal satisfaction and a genuine passion for the sport, are more likely to sustain their involvement and achieve higher levels of achievement over the long term. Athletes rely on focus and attention to remain fully present, perform skills with precision, and make calculated choices in competitive situations. Athletes can improve their ability to handle pressure and perform better by utilizing effective stress management techniques. These approaches enable athletes to regulate their physiological and psychological reactions to stress, resulting in reduced anxiety levels. In order to achieve optimal sports performance, it is crucial to build robust psychological skills (Ryan & Deci, 2020; Weinberg & Gould, 2019). Interventions and training programs designed to improve psychological skills in athletes typically involve a blend of instruction, practical application, and constructive criticism. An effective method often used is mental skills training (MST), which involves the utilization of strategies such as visualization, goal planning, relaxation, and self-talk. Visualization is athletes engaging in mental rehearsal of their performance, which has the potential to bolster confidence and boost execution in real competitions. Goal setting enables athletes to establish precise, quantifiable, achievable, meaningful, and time-limited (SMART) goals, which offer a distinct trajectory for personal growth (Locke & Latham, 2019).

Another efficacious technique is mindfulness training, which assists athletes in cultivating heightened awareness and mastery over their thoughts and emotions. Engaging in mindfulness techniques, such as meditation and breathing exercises, can enhance concentration, alleviate stress, and promote general well-being. Cognitive-behavioral approaches (CBT) are employed to assist athletes in recognizing and questioning detrimental cognitive processes, substituting them with affirmative and productive ones. These programs are frequently customized to meet the specific requirements of the athletes, guaranteeing that the interventions target precise areas for enhancement. Coaches and sports psychologists have a vital role in executing these programs and offering continuous support and feedback to assist athletes in enhancing and perfecting their psychological abilities (Weinberg & Gould, 2019; Gucciardi et al., 2009).

Statement of the Problem

Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 16 July 2024

Accepted: 23 July 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

153

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.12798065](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12798065)

The athletic performance of secondary school students in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area (LGA) in Rivers State, Nigeria, seems to be affected by several psychological issues that are not thoroughly comprehended or properly addressed. Although these students are showing a growing interest and involvement in sports, there is a noticeable lack of organized training in psychological skills that are crucial for improving sports performance. The absence of emphasis on psychological training may impede athletes from reaching their utmost capabilities and performing at their best in competitive environments.

Furthermore, the current body of research examining the relationship between psychological skills and sports performance among secondary school students in Nigeria, particularly in the Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA, is lacking in scope and depth. It is crucial to investigate the influence of factors such as motivation, self-confidence, attention, concentration, stress management, and goal setting on the athletic performance of these children. In the absence of a thorough comprehension and focused interventions, secondary school athletes may persist in encountering difficulties in optimizing their performance potential. This study aims to address this deficiency by investigating the correlation between psychological skills and sports performance. The findings will offer valuable knowledge for coaches, educators, and policymakers to design training programs that can improve the overall performance and well-being of young athletes in this area.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the correlations between psychological skills and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State. Specifically this study intends to:

1. Find out the correlation between motivation and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State
2. Determine the correlation between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

3. Examine the correlation between concentration and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State
4. Ascertain the correlation between stress management and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State
5. Investigate the correlation between goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were generated for the research

1. what is the correlation between motivation and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State?
2. what is the correlation between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State?
3. what is the correlation between concentration and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State?
4. what is the correlation between stress management and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State?
5. what is the correlation between goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated and tested at .05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant correlation between motivation and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant correlation between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.
3. There is no significant correlation between concentration and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.
4. There is no significant correlation between stress management and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.
5. There is no significant correlation between stress goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design. This research design establishes the relationship between independent and dependent variables in a study. The population of the study consists of all public secondary school students in Obio/Akpor local government area of Rivers State. A sample size of 450 secondary school students was used for the study. The researcher used proportionate stratified random sampling technique with 30% of the population of each of the selected school to draw the sample in order to provide equal chances of participation for the students. The researcher selected 450 respondents (students) to respond to the research questionnaire. Psychological Skills and Sports Performance Enhancement Questionnaire (RPSSPEQ). There were 5 questions for each research question, that is, 30 research questions in total. It was used to investigate the relationship between psychological skills and sports performance enhancement. Test re-test method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument. To obtain the reliability of the instrument, the researcher administered twenty (20) copies of questionnaire to ten (20) secondary school students in Ikwere Local Government Area that were not used for the research but shares similar characteristics with the study group. After

two weeks, the same numbers of copies of questionnaire were re-administered to the same respondents of the same school. After that, the researcher used the Pearson Product Moment correlation and a coefficient value of 0.72 was obtained indicating that the instrument was reliability. 450 copies of questionnaire were distributed among the respondents but 430 copies were retrieved giving a return rate of 95.5 per cent. The data collected were carefully sorted, coded and analyzed using mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The criterion mean for accepting an item was 2.50. Any item mean from 2.50 and above represented agree while mean values below 2.50 were disagree.

Table 1: Correlation of motivation and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remarks
1	I am aware of the concept of motivation and its potential impact on my sports performance.	30% (129)	40% (172)	20% (86)	10% (43)	3.25	1.89	Agree
2	I believe that using motivation can improve my confidence and performance in sports.	20% (86)	35% (151)	30% (129)	15% (64)	2.60	1.14	Agree
3	I understand the different types of motivation and how they can influence my performance.	25% (108)	30% (129)	25% (108)	20% (85)	2.70	1.01	Agree
4	I feel confident in my ability to use motivation effectively to enhance my sports performance.	15% (64)	45% (194)	25% (108)	15% (64)	2.80	0.66	Agree
5	I believe that incorporating intrinsic into my training routine can positively impact my sports performance.	25% (108)	40% (172)	20% (86)	15% (64)	3.15	1.23	Agree
Grand mean						2.90		

RESULTS

Table 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the students' perceptions of the role of motivation in enhancing sports performance among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State. The overall grand mean of 2.90 indicates a general agreement that motivation positively impacts sports performance. Specifically, the highest mean score (3.25) and substantial agreement (70%) on awareness of motivation's potential impact highlight that most students recognize the importance of motivation in sports. The statement about the belief that using motivation can improve confidence and performance received a lower mean score of 2.60, yet 55% of students still agreed, suggesting a positive perception but also indicating some skepticism. Understanding different types of motivation had a mean score of

2.70, with 55% agreeing, showing moderate comprehension among students. Confidence in using motivation effectively had a mean score of 2.80, with 60% agreement, reflecting a reasonable level of self-assuredness in applying motivational techniques. The belief in the impact of intrinsic motivation on sports performance had a mean score of 3.15, with 65% agreeing, underscoring a strong acknowledgment of the value of self-driven motivation. These findings suggest that while students generally recognize the benefits of motivation for sports performance, there is variability in their confidence and understanding, indicating a need for enhanced educational and motivational strategies to fully optimize their sports potential.

Table 2: Correlation of self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remarks
1	I have received information about the importance of self-efficacy for sports performance enhancement.	10% (43)	20% (86)	40% (172)	30% (129)	2.45	1.65	Disagree
2	I believe that having confidence in my abilities can positively impact my sports performance.	15% (64)	25% (108)	35% (151)	25% (108)	2.60	1.08	Agree
3	I feel confident in my ability to overcome challenges and obstacles in sports.	20% (86)	30% (129)	30% (129)	20% (86)	2.60	1.13	Agree
4	I understand that believing in myself and my skills can enhance my performance in sports.	10% (43)	20% (86)	35% (151)	35% (151)	2.35	1.33	Disagree
5	I recognize that having a strong belief in my own capabilities can lead to better sports performance.	25% (108)	50% (215)	15% (64)	10% (43)	3.35	0.88	Agree
Grand mean						2.67		Agree

The analysis of Table 2, which examines the correlation between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA, reveals mixed perceptions about the role of self-confidence in sports. The grand mean score of 2.67 indicates an overall agreement that self-confidence positively impacts sports performance. However, individual item analysis shows variability. For instance, only 30% of students ($\bar{x} = 2.45$) agree they are aware of the importance of self-confidence, highlighting a significant gap in knowledge dissemination. Despite this, 40% of students ($\bar{x} = 2.60$) believe that confidence can improve performance, showing a more favorable view. Similarly, the same mean score (2.60) and split agreement (20% strongly agreed, 30% agreed) suggest that students feel somewhat confident in overcoming challenges. The lowest mean score ($\bar{x} = 2.35$) indicates that many students disagree with their ability to use motivation effectively, signaling a need for better motivational training. The highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 3.35$) for incorporating intrinsic motivation suggests that students recognize the value of self-driven motivation. Overall, while students acknowledge the importance of self-confidence, there is a clear need for enhanced educational efforts and practical strategies to build and sustain this psychological skill to optimize sports performance.

Table 3: Correlation of concentration and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remarks
1	I understand that concentration is important for improving my sports performance.	20% (86)	30% (129)	30% (129)	20% (86)	2.70	1.00	Agree
2	I believe that being able to maintain focus and concentration can enhance my sports performance.	10% (43)	20% (86)	40% (172)	30% (129)	2.60	1.08	Agree
3	I believe that practicing concentration techniques can positively impact my sports performance.	25% (108)	35% (151)	25% (108)	15% (64)	2.60	1.13	Agree
4	I recognize that concentration can help me make better decisions and execute skills effectively in sports.	20% (86)	30% (129)	30% (129)	20% (86)	2.35	1.33	Disagree
5	I feel confident in my ability to stay focused and concentrated during sports activities.	15% (64)	25% (108)	30% (129)	30% (129)	3.35	0.88	Agree
Grand mean						2.67		Agree

The analysis of Table 3, which explores the relationship between concentration and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Obio/Akpor LGA, reveals an overall positive perception of the importance of concentration in sports, with a grand mean of 2.67 indicating general agreement. Most students (50%) agree that concentration is important for improving sports performance, with a mean score of 2.70. Similarly, the belief that maintaining focus can enhance performance is moderately supported (30% agreed, mean = 2.60), although a significant portion of students (40%) disagreed, suggesting some uncertainty. The recognition of the positive impact of practicing concentration techniques received stronger support, with 60% agreement (mean = 2.60), reflecting a recognition of its benefits. The statement about concentration aiding in decision-making and skill execution had a mixed response, with an equal split between agreement and disagreement (50% agreed, mean = 2.35). Lastly, confidence in the ability to stay focused during sports activities was moderately supported (40% agreed, mean = 3.35), though some students lacked confidence. Overall, the findings highlight that while students generally recognize the importance of concentration for sports performance, there is variability in their confidence and belief in their ability to maintain focus, suggesting a need for targeted interventions to enhance concentration skills in sports.

Table 4: Correlation of stress management and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remarks
1	I understand that being able to manage my daily activities is important for improving my sports performance.	20% (86)	30% (129)	30% (129)	20% (86)	2.70	1.65	Agree
2	I feel relaxed in my ability to manage every task during sports activities.	10% (43)	20% (86)	40% (172)	30% (129)	2.05	1.15	Disagree
3	I recognize that managing can help me make better decisions and enhance my sports performance	25% (108)	35% (151)	25% (108)	15% (64)	2.95	1.25	Agree
4	I believe that practicing relaxation techniques can positively impact my sports performance.	20% (86)	30% (129)	30% (129)	20% (86)	2.70	1.00	Agree
5	Stress cannot be managed by athletes alone	15% (64)	25% (108)	30% (129)	30% (129)	2.45	1.65	Disagree
Grandmean						2.67		Agree

Table 4 presents an analysis of the correlation between stress management and sports performance enhancement among secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA. The overall grand mean of 2.57 suggests that students generally agree on the importance of stress management in enhancing sports performance. Specifically, 50% of the students agree that managing daily activities is important for sports performance (mean = 2.70), indicating a substantial recognition of the need for organizational skills. However, confidence in managing every task during sports activities is lower, with only 30% agreement (mean = 2.05), highlighting a potential area for improvement. The belief that stress management can enhance decision-making and performance is strongly supported, with 60% of students agreeing (mean = 2.95). Practicing relaxation techniques is also widely recognized as beneficial, with 50% agreement (mean = 2.70). On the other hand, the belief that athletes cannot manage stress alone had mixed responses, with 30% disagreement (mean = 2.45), indicating a need for external support. These findings underscore the critical role of stress management in sports performance and the necessity for targeted interventions to enhance stress management skills among students.

Table 5: Correlation of Goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remarks
1	I am aware of the importance of setting specific goals to improve my sports performance.	40% (172)	35% (151)	15% (64)	10% (43)	3.40	0.94	Agree
2	I believe that setting measurable goals can help me track my progress in sports.	35% (151)	40% (172)	20% (86)	5% (21)	3.30	0.42	Agree
3	I have received information or education about the benefits of goal setting for sports performance enhancement.	25% (108)	30% (129)	25% (108)	20% (86)	2.70	1.39	Agree
4	I understand the relevance of setting goals that align with my sports aspirations and abilities.	20% (86)	30% (129)	30% (129)	20% (86)	2.50	1.40	Agree
5	I believe that setting time-bound goals can help me stay focused and motivated in sports.	25% (108)	35% (151)	20% (86)	20% (86)	2.95	1.05	Agree
Grandmean						2.97		Agree

The analysis of Table 5 highlights the correlation between goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA. The overall grand mean of 2.97 indicates a general agreement on the importance of goal-setting in sports. Notably, awareness of the importance of setting specific goals scored the highest mean (3.40) with 75% of students agreeing, showing strong recognition of its value. The belief in measurable goals to track progress was also well-supported with a mean of 3.30 and 75% agreement, indicating a clear understanding of the benefits of measurable goals. Information or education about goal-setting received moderate agreement (55%, mean = 2.70), suggesting that while many students are informed, there is still room for more education. Understanding the relevance of aligning goals with aspirations and abilities also showed moderate agreement (50%, mean = 2.50), highlighting a need for better alignment practices. Lastly, the belief in the motivational power of time-bound goals had mixed responses with a mean of 2.95 and 60% agreement, showing some skepticism. These findings underscore the importance of goal-setting in enhancing sports performance and suggest the need for comprehensive goal-setting education to fully leverage its benefits.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant correlation between motivation and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.

Table 6: Simple linear regression model showing correlation of motivation and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

Model	R	R ²	df	P	Remark
Constant	0.89	0.79	1	.000 (p < 0.05)	Significant
Sport Performance Enhancement			& 430		

The analysis of hypothesis 1 and table 6 revealed compelling findings regarding the correlation between motivation and sports performance enhancement among secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA. The significant correlation coefficient (R = 0.89) indicates a strong positive relationship between motivation and sports performance enhancement. This suggests that as motivation increases, sports performance enhancement also tends to increase among the students studied. The coefficient of determination (R² = 0.79) indicated that 79% of the variance in sports performance enhancement can be attributed to motivation. This high value suggests that motivation plays a substantial role in predicting and influencing sports performance outcomes among the students. The probability value (P = .000) is less than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, indicating that the observed correlation coefficient is statistically significant. This means that the likelihood of observing such a strong correlation between motivation and sports performance enhancement by random chance is very low.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant correlation between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.

Table 7: Simple linear regression model showing correlation of self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

Model	R	R ²	df	P	Remark
Constant Sport Performance Enhancement	0.85	0.72	1 & 430	.000 (p< 0.05)	Significant

The analysis of Hypothesis 2 and Table 6 reveals important insights into the correlation between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA. The significant correlation coefficient ($R = 0.85$) indicates a strong positive relationship between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement. This suggests that as self-confidence increases, sports performance enhancement also tends to increase among the students studied. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.72$) indicates that 72% of the variance in sports performance enhancement can be attributed to self-confidence. This high value signifies that self-confidence is a substantial predictor of sports performance among the students. The probability value ($P = .000$) is less than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, indicating that the observed correlation coefficient is statistically significant. This means that the likelihood of observing such a strong correlation between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement by random chance is very low.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant correlation between concentration and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.

Table 8: Simple linear regression model showing correlation concentration and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

Model	R	R ²	df	P	Remark
Constant Sport Performance Enhancement	0.82	0.67	1 & 430	.000 (p< 0.05)	Significant

The analysis of Hypothesis 3 and Table 8 provides valuable insights into the correlation between concentration and sports performance enhancement among secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA. The significant correlation coefficient (R = 0.82) indicates a strong positive relationship between concentration and sports performance enhancement. This suggests that as concentration improves, sports performance enhancement also tends to improve among the students studied. The coefficient of determination (R² = 0.67) indicates that 67% of the variance in sports performance enhancement can be attributed to concentration. This high value signifies that concentration is a substantial predictor of sports performance among the students. Effective concentration enables athletes to focus on their tasks, make better decisions, and execute skills more efficiently, which directly impacts their performance. The probability value (P = .000) is less than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, indicating that the observed correlation coefficient is statistically significant. This means that the likelihood of observing such a strong correlation between concentration and sports performance enhancement by random chance is very low.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant correlation between stress management and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.

Table 9: Simple linear regression model showing correlation of stress management and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

Model	R	R ²	df	P	Remark
Constant Sport Performance Enhancement	0.89	0.79	1 & 430	.000 (p< 0.05)	Significant

The analysis of Hypothesis 4 and Table 9 provides critical insights into the correlation between stress management and sports performance enhancement among secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA. The significant correlation coefficient ($R = 0.89$) indicates a very strong positive relationship between stress management and sports performance enhancement. This suggests that as stress management skills improve, sports performance enhancement also significantly improves among the students studied. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.79$) indicates that 79% of the variance in sports performance enhancement can be attributed to stress management. This exceptionally high value signifies that stress management is a major predictor of sports performance among the students. The probability value ($P = .000$) is less than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, indicating that the observed correlation coefficient is statistically significant. This means that the likelihood of observing such a strong correlation between stress management and sports performance enhancement by random chance is extremely low.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant correlation between stress goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State.

Table 10: Simple linear regression model showing correlation of goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State

Model	R	R ²	df	P	Remark
Constant Sport Performance Enhancement	0.92	0.85	1 & 430	.000 (p< 0.05)	Significant

The analysis of Hypothesis 5 and Table 10 provides crucial insights into the correlation between goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA. The significant correlation coefficient ($R = 0.92$) indicates a very strong positive relationship between goal-setting and sports performance enhancement. This suggests that as students engage in effective goal-setting, their sports performance enhancement significantly improves. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.85$) indicates that 85% of the variance in sports performance enhancement can be attributed to goal-setting. The probability value ($P = .000$) is less than the conventional alpha level of 0.05, indicating that the observed correlation coefficient is statistically significant. This means that the likelihood of observing such a strong correlation between goal-setting and sports performance enhancement by random chance is extremely low.

DISCUSSION

The finding of table 1 revealed that there is a significant correlation between motivation and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State. The results is in line with the finding of (Ryan & Deci, 2020) who posited that the significance of motivation lies in its ability to propel athletes towards constant training, continuous self-improvement, and effective competition. The substantial mean scores and high percentages of agreement presented in table 1 demonstrate that students possess a clear understanding of the influence of motivation on their academic achievement and have strong confidence in its effectiveness. This is consistent with the findings of Vallerand (2007) who highlighted that the importance of intrinsic motivation, which is motivated by personal objectives and enjoyment of the activity. Intrinsic motivation leads to prolonged effort and improved performance outcomes.

Similarly, the finding of table 2 shows that there is a significant correlation between self-confidence and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State. Vealey & Chase, (2016) supported this study because according to them self-confidence is of utmost importance in athletics as it empowers players to confront difficult situations, bounce back from failures, and excel in their performance. The divergent results presented in Table 2, with certain assertions demonstrating robust consensus while others indicating discord, imply differing degrees of self-confidence among students. This finding is supported the study of (Bandura, 1997) who posited that for students to maintain optimum sports performance there is need for therapies focused on enhancing self-confidence through efficient training and psychological assistance.

The findings of table 3 revealed that there is a significant correlation between concentration and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State. This finding is in lieu with the findings of Weinberg & Gould, (2019) who opined that concentration is crucial for athletes to proficiently perform abilities and make tactical judgements during competition. The data presented in table 3 demonstrates a predominantly favourable perspective about the significance of focus in athletic achievement. Nevertheless, the assertion about the level of confidence in maintaining focus exhibits a combination of reactions, indicating possible difficulties in sustaining concentration

when faced with stress or pressure. According to Williams et al., (2004) this emphasizes the necessity of implementing training programmes that improve the ability to focus and the psychological strength of student-athletes.

The finding of table 4 clearly shows that there is a statistically significant correlation between stress management and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State. This finding is supported by the study of Hanton et al., (2015) who asserted that efficient stress management is essential for maintaining peak performance levels when faced with demand. The results shown in Table 4 indicate a generally favourable impression of the significance of stress management, however there is some divergence of opinion regarding the capacity of athletes to handle stress independently. Furthermore, Fletcher & Sarkar, (2012) also stated that this finding highlights the necessity of implementing thorough stress management training and support systems in sports programmes to assist students in cultivating efficient coping mechanisms.

Finally the finding of table 5 revealed that there is a significant correlation between goal-setting and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni LGA of Rivers State. This finding is supported by the findings of Locke & Latham, (2019) who stated that it is essential for athletes to establish SMART goals, which are clear, measurable, realistic, relevant, and time-bound, in order to maintain concentration, motivation, and monitor their progress. According to Amasiatu (2006), it has been shown that setting goals has an impact on various aspects of athletic performance, including direction, intensity, and persistence. The results shown in table 5 also demonstrated a robust acknowledgement of the advantages of goal-setting, especially in relation to the understanding and confidence in its effectiveness. Nevertheless Burton et al., (2011) argued that there are doubts over the effectiveness of objectives with specific time limits indicate a requirement for additional instruction on goal-setting techniques specifically designed for sports environments. Amasiatu (2006) also supported this idea when he asserted that the challenge lies not in facilitating goal identification among individuals, but rather in guiding them to establish optimal objectives that offer clear direction, boost motivation, and enable successful goal attainment.

Conclusion

The study examined the correlation between selected psychological skills and sports performance enhancement among government secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. The analysis of the data revealed significant positive relationships between sports performance enhancement and several psychological constructs: motivation, self-confidence, concentration, goal-setting, and stress management. Motivation was found to be a crucial factor in enhancing sports performance, as students who reported higher levels of motivation demonstrated better sports outcomes. Self-confidence similarly showed a strong correlation with sports performance, indicating that athletes who believe in their abilities are more likely to perform well. The ability to concentrate was also positively correlated with sports performance, underscoring the importance of focus and attention in athletic success. Goal-setting emerged as another significant factor, with students who set clear and achievable goals displaying improved sports performance. Finally, effective stress management was found to be crucial for maintaining optimal performance levels, especially under pressure.

Recommendations

1. Sports administrators and coaches should integrate training modules on motivation, self-confidence, concentration, goal-setting, and stress management into their regular training programs. These skills should be emphasized as core components of athlete development.
2. Organize regular workshops and interactive sessions led by sports psychologists to educate student-athletes on the importance of psychological skills in sports. These sessions can provide practical techniques and strategies for developing these skills.
3. Make resources such as books, articles, and online materials on sports psychology readily available to students. This will enable them to learn more about different psychological skills and techniques at their own pace.
4. Conduct specialized training programs for sports administrators to enhance their understanding and application of sports psychology. This will equip them with the knowledge and tools to effectively support and develop student-athletes.

5. Encourage student-athletes to actively utilize psychological skills in their training and competition. Providing a supportive environment where students can practice and refine these skills can lead to significant improvements in their sports performance.
6. Implement a system for regularly monitoring and evaluating the psychological skill development of student-athletes. This can help in identifying areas that need further improvement and in tailoring training programs to meet the specific needs of the athletes.

REFERENCES

- Amaele, S., & Enunwaonye, A. (2020). The impact of sports participation on secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(30), 78-85.
- Amasiatu, A.N., (2006). An examination on the empirical test of the theory on goal-setting on sports performance. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas*, 15(1), 218-229
- Burton, D., Gillham, A., & Glenn, S. (2011). *Advances in Motivation in Sport and Exercise* (3rd ed.). Human Kinetics.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2020). *Intrinsic Motivation and Self-Determination in Human Behavior*. Springer.
- Fletcher, D., & Sarkar, M. (2012). A grounded theory of psychological resilience in Olympic champions. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 13(5), 669-678. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2012.04.007>
- Gucciardi, D. F., Gordon, S., & Dimmock, J. A. (2009). Development and preliminary validation of a mental toughness inventory for Australian football. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 10(1), 201-209.
- Hanton, S., Fletcher, D., & Coughlan, G. (2015). Stress in elite sport performers: A comparative study of competitive and organizational stressors. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 23(10), 1129-1141.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2019). *A Theory of Goal Setting and Task Performance*. Prentice Hall.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2019). Goal setting theory: Controversies and resolutions. In *Advances in Motivation Science* (Vol. 6, pp. 145-188). Elsevier.
- McArdle, S., Martin, C., Lennon, A., & Moore, P. (2015). Testing a dual process model of self-control on events in sport. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 21, 51-58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2015.04.003>
- McArdle, W. D., Katch, F. I., & Katch, V. L. (2015). *Exercise Physiology: Nutrition, Energy, and Human Performance*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2020). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 54-67.
- Sheard, M., Golby, J., & van Wersch, A. (2009). Progress towards construct validation of the Sports Mental Toughness Questionnaire (SMTQ). *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 25(3), 186-193.
- Vallerand, R. J. (2007). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in sport and exercise: A review and a look at the future. In G. Tenenbaum & R. C. Eklund (Eds.), *Handbook of Sport Psychology* (3rd ed., pp. 59-83). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118270011.ch3>
- Vealey, R. S., & Chase, M. A. (2016). Self-confidence in sport: Conceptual and research advances. In *Advances in Sport and Exercise Psychology* (pp. 65-97). Human Kinetics.
- Weinberg, R. S., & Gould, D. (2019). *Foundations of Sport and Exercise Psychology* (7th ed.). Human Kinetics.